

A Study Showing the Impact of E-Marketing on Consumer Purchase Behaviour

Abhishek Tibrewal, Zarafshaan Malaika Nadeem,
MBA, Universal Business School, Karjat, Raigad, Maharashtra, 410201

Abstract:- Consumer Purchase Behaviour is one of the most sought-after fields of study in the Marketing analytics sector, since it enables companies to better understand their customers' purchasing behaviours, resulting in more revenues at a rapid growth rate. In today's environment, marketing isn't just about using simple tools and strategies for promotional goals; it also involves getting to know your customers on a deeper level and effectively predicting their next move. Companies that can anticipate with more precision are those who are leading global market trends, and with a deeper understanding, they are even inventing their own trends. One of the best places to see the impact of these tactics is through e-marketing. The study will look into the numerous Emarketing tools and tactics, as well as the influence of consumer buying behaviour on them. The growth of Internet usage has introduced a new way of marketing and distributing products and services. The consumer may purchase the product of their choice with just a few clicks, so the Internet has been shown to be time-saving and convenient. Consumer behaviour towards E-marketing is presented systematically in this paper. The main objective of the study is to analyse the consumer perceptions of E-marketing on the basis of the findings of the study. The study is based on both primary & secondary data. The pandemic situation has been taken into account and primary data will be done by knowing Customer Perception towards E-Marketing through survey and secondary data will be taken from reference paper. Both primary & secondary data will be analysed to compare the consumer perception of the E-Marketing field in the post-pandemic situation. With increased internet literacy, India's prospects for online marketing are increasing. Flipkart, Myntra, Amazon, Ajo are few of the E-commerce companies impacting the Consumer Perceptions towards E-Marketing field.

Keywords:- Consumer Purchase behaviour, E-marketing, Consumer Perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

E-marketing is the marketing of products and services through electronic media. E-marketing is one of the most recent and rising marketing methods. It includes the creative application of internet technology, such as the use of various multimedia, graphics, text, and other elements in conjunction with many languages to produce appealing advertisements, forms, and an e-shop where products may be viewed, promoted, and sold. E-marketing does not just imply the creation or promotion of a website, nor the placement of a banner ad on another website. Advertising

(flash, text, graphics, audio, or video), product display, product navigation, 3-D product view, basket selection, checkout, and payment are all included. The phrases e-marketing and internet marketing are interchangeable.

A. Type of Marketing in a variety of Business Formats:

- **E-commerce** - Refers to the direct sale of items to the general public or businesses.
- **Lead-generation websites**, such as policy bazaar and Sulekha, where sales leads are generated and either sold to a third party or used in-house to convert into sales through the proper channel.
- **Affiliate marketing** is a type of referral marketing in which a reward is paid for suggesting a product, company, or website to other friends, relatives, or other possible customers or target segments.
- **Video Marketing**—A picture is worth a thousand words, and a video is worth thousands of pictures. One can captivate the attention and emotions of a possible target market through video marketing. When it comes to video marketing, the "correct message to the right audience" is key.
- **Email marketing**—Email marketing is thought to be the most efficient and effective because the target customer's index is already known. Sending emails to a specific market is now not only inexpensive but also incredibly successful.
- **Social media marketing**— Social media is a great way to contact customers directly to increase product awareness and maintain brand loyalty. It can be done on LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Google+, and YouTube, among other social media platforms.

B. Characteristics of Social Media Marketing:

- More sales result from increased brand recognition and reputation.
- Increased product loyalty can be achieved by direct connection with potential customers.
- Businesses may boost the number of visitors to their website by optimising it for search.
- Businesses will have a better understanding of their consumers' demands by targeting a specific audience.

C. Benefits of E-Marketing

- It aids in achieving a considerably higher return on investment than traditional marketing by increasing sales income at a low cost.
- When it comes to cost, E-marketing means lower marketing campaign costs because the marketing is done via the internet and only paid advertisements can be considered a cost for the company, aside from the wage of digital media staff.
- The most important benefit is that the campaigns' results

are visible and quick, which helps to target the proper customers.

- E-marketing is a very efficient and effective instrument to use in the current business context because it is easy to monitor through online tracking capabilities.

D. Limitations of E-Marketing

- E-marketing is completely reliant on technology and the internet; taking a shortcut could risk the entire organisation.
- The presence of global competition is both a benefit and a threat.
- Because data is accessible to anybody, privacy and security concerns are considerable; as a result, users should exercise extreme caution when using the internet.
- Businesses must spend a lot of money to be secure when privacy and security concerns are strong.
- In today's ever-changing technical environment, businesses must adapt at the speed of technology, and maintenance expenses can rise as the size of the company grows.

For both the customer and the marketer, E-marketing is more convenient than traditional marketing. It provides a huge number of variants for a given product at relatively affordable pricing. Customers must be knowledgeable with the latest innovations in digital technology, as well as the financial and legal domains, in order to use E-commerce. In this way, its appeal is limited due to the need for high-speed Internet connections, overly complicated websites, and, from the buyer's perspective, the inability of customers to touch, taste, smell, or have a trial before making an online purchase, the most serious of which is the concern about security with online payments, among other factors.

Consumers are very concerned about the quality of a product or service as they search for the best quality, the mindset of consumers to buy their favourite brand and their involvement in the purchase process, some people are aware of new trends, alternate choices of products or too many products, and consumers have the tendency to exhibit price and value are all important factors affecting E-marketing.

As a result, the internet has become a medium that has aided individuals in living a simpler life. It has aided people in discovering new ways of accomplishing things that were previously done in a much more sophisticated manner. This research investigates consumer behaviour in the context of E-marketing.

II. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study emphasizes on the consumer behaviour towards e-marketing. At any given point of time, there are billions of people online and they're the potential customers for a company providing online sale of products. Due to the rapid advancement in the Internet, and they're the potential customers for a company providing online sale of products. Due to the rapid advancement in the Internet, a company interested in selling products from its website will constantly has to search for an edge in the

competition. Since there are huge potential barriers, it is of the utmost importance to understand what the consumer wants & needs.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The extensive growth in the field of buying & selling has led the businesses to understand that what actually motivates the consumers to shop online. As the online shopping has become a customary medium, it has become important to perceive the consumers behaviour in the field of E-Marketing. That's why it is essential to analyze, identify and interpret the elements which could clout consumers to shop online. Also, a detailed study about the e-marketing in the times of pandemic is required in order to promote businesses for their survival.

IV. OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH

Objective of our research study: -

- To examine the impact of e-marketing on purchase decision of consumers.
- To assess the impact of Covid-19 on e-marketing in context to consumer purchase pattern.
- To analyse the level of satisfaction of customers in e-marketing.

V. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study was conducted during coronavirus pandemic times so instead of field survey, online questionnaire was preferred and also secondary datasets like pre-published research works were taken into account.
- The study emphasizes only on consumer behaviour towards electronic marketing and geographical location was confined to India only.
- The information collected might not be able to, generalize in the world, due to the location & the sample size taken.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section deals with the design of the study, methodology, target population, sample size & sampling techniques. To test the proposed objectives, we adopted a descriptive study and Factor analysis test is performed to find the result.

A. DATA COLLECTION METHODS

The primary data are those, which was collected afresh for the first time, and thus happens to be original character. With reference to this study, data was collected through online questionnaire. It is a fresh data, which was collected from the consumer by filling up of questionnaire.

B. PRIMARY DATA

Primary data is collected through questionnaire.

C. SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data will be collected from various sources like journals, previous reports and websites.

D. TARGET POPULATION

In general, the study has no specified age limit, but the population represented the Residents of India.

E. QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN

The questionnaire comprised of two sections. The first section gathered information on the demographic profiles & valued respondents as per their quantitative behaviour. Questions about gender, income details, age etc. were asked & certain questions related to consumer awareness were asked. The second part of the questionnaire consisted of questions related to consumer perception identification. The questionnaire was developed using one-item scale and five-point Likert scale.

F. SAMPLING

For the purpose of the analysis, 100 respondents have been selected as sample size. A sampling Method is the identification of the specific process by which the entities of the sample have been selected. In this research we have used convenience sampling method for the easiness of data collection and respondents are selected from different descriptive profiles.

G. STATISTICAL TOOL USED

- Simple percentage analysis
- Weighted score ranking analysis

H. SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage refers to special kind of ratio, percentage is used in making comparison between two or more series of data percentage are used to describe relationship. Since the percentage reduce everything to a common base and here by all meaningful comparison to be made.

Simple percentage = $\frac{\text{Actual respondents}}{\text{Total respondents}} * 100$

I. WEIGHTED SCORE RANKING ANALYSIS

In this method weights of the various aspects of factors are obtained by multiplying the rank given with the frequency, it gives the weighted score, on the basis of the weighted score the rank will be given.

VII. LITERATURE REVIEW

Amar Alhamad Alsayah (2020) Online shopping has become a part of the modern person's daily routine and has had a significant impact on his diverse consuming patterns, both favourably and badly. As a result, one of the most important aspects of this consumer's behaviours in the implementation of online shopping operations is to study and analyses it so that businesses may understand it and steer it toward their objectives.

Komalpreet Kaur et al. (2021) This research paper will delve into numerous E-marketing tools and tactics, as well as the influence of customer buying behaviour on them. The study is based on both primary and secondary data, and it has undergone tests such as factor analysis and correlation to ensure its accuracy. The pandemic scenario has been considered, and the study's distinctiveness resides in the suggestions it makes to strengthen business strategy,

particularly for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. As a result, this study serves the objective of better understanding consumer behaviour in the field of E-marketing. the purpose of understanding the consumer behaviour in the E-marketing field.

Malvika Tomar et al. (2019) This research paper will tell us about research Technology Acceptance model study which has numerous practical and managerial applications and gives insightful information to the marketers to spend more on their digital marketing and how to create effective but customized social media, live interaction digital marketing campaigns, emailer so that they could target the potential of e-marketing and its humongous online consumer base. Also, it gives directions about how to develop new theories studying the effect of digital marketing strategies in an offline environment.

Ms. Neethu N Kumar et al. (2017) This paper has been designed to examine the key consumer behaviour and their relationship with each other in the e-marketing perspective. The entire research study was conducted in the Ernakulam district. The study had a sample size of 200 and it gives the direction to improve the delivery and advertising web-products & services process to achieve the objective of E-marketing and E-commerce in the long run process.

Shailja Bhakar et al. (2019) The main aim of this research paper is identifying the impact of e-advertisement on purchase intentions of consumers. The study was conducted on a sample size of 276 respondents identified using non probability purposive sampling technique. The results indicated significant impact of social networking was found on Brand recognition and the effectiveness of e-advertisement further Brand recognition was found to be having 8 significant effects on consumer purchase intention.

Dr. Parul Deshwal (2016) This research study focuses on analyzing different types of online advertising and explore how online advertisements affect consumers purchasing behaviour.

Jomon Varkey Vellayil et al. (2020) The aim of this study is to analyse the significant relation between e-advertisement appeals, attitude, and purchase behaviour based on nationality. An electronic questionnaire was used for data collection from seven countries India, Pakistan, Morocco, South Africa, Brazil, Laos and Cambodia where culture and beliefs are basically different. Altogether 270 responses were analysed by cross-tabulation. Study results explain that there are statistically significant relations between e-advertising's appeals (information, credibility, privacy, irritation), attitude (negative attitudes towards a company because of an irritating ad), purchase behaviour (negative purchase behaviours due to irritating advertising) and nationality.

Jose Martins et al. (2017) It's critical to understand what drives consumers to interact with smartphone adverts and, as a result, what drives them to make a purchase. We suggested a conceptual model that blends Ducoffe's web advertising model and flow experience theory to attain this purpose. We empirically tested the conceptual model using a partial least squares (PLS) estimation based on data collected from 303 Portuguese respondents. Purchase intention is explained by advertising value, flow experience, online design quality, and brand awareness, according to the findings. The findings of the study enable marketers and advertisers to better understand how smartphone commercials influence customer purchase intent.

Dani, N. J. (2017) This paper talked about consumer's attitude towards online shopping and the factors associated with it. The study was conducted in Kanyakumari and 100 was allotted sample size. This paper talked about security features as a major concern among consumers and derived its solutions from those researches. Research work's limitation was its time & budget.

Aditi Srivastava et al. (2016) Marketers have attempted to contact the audience on the digital platform in a variety of methods. They've devised a number of ways for people to contact them via the internet. Consumers primarily utilize desktops/laptops, mobile phones (smart phone/feature phone), and tablets. This research aims to provide a comprehensive picture of how consumer behaviour has changed as a result of online initiatives targeted at increasing online consumer engagement, traffic, and conversions.

Dr. Sanjay Hooda et al. (2012) This paper examines the key consumer behaviour attribute and relation among them in E-marketing perspective. Attempt has been made to study the acceptance rate of e-marketing among the Jaipur consumers and its impact on their purchase decision.

T. Siva Kumar et al. (2019) The aim of the study is to examine the implication of digital marketing in consumer purchase decision and to find out that the consumers are aware of digital marketing and the digital channels influence in their purchase decision.

Dr. Komal Nagrani et al. (2021) This paper talked about consumer's attitude towards online shopping and the factors associated with it.

VIII. FACTORS IMPACT ON CUSTOMER PURCHASE DECISION

The customer purchasing decision is impacted by the factors that are willing to engage the customer in internet shopping. There is a positive impact of e-marketing on consumer decisionmaking by providing a variety of options to the customers, product comparison, information screening, and dependability.

A. Cost Efficiency

The pricing influences the purchasing decisions of customers. It is the attribute that is visible and dominant. The companies are providing a lower cost in online purchasing for attracting customers towards online purchasing.

B. Information Satisfaction

The information provided by the organization regarding products and services offered impacts on overall customer satisfaction. The user interface quality and information quality impact on information satisfaction.

C. Customer Trust

The companies develop e-marketing strategies for marketing efficiency that add value to the business as compared to traditional marketing. It is challenging for companies to develop trust through interconnecting technology.

D. Internet Shopping Experience

The customer with positive customer experience develops perception towards online shopping. They are also influenced by an online review that influences customer purchasing behaviour.

IX. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Gender

Gender	Response
Female	40
Male	61
Grand Total	101

Fig. 1: Gender

The chart shows that out of the total 101 respondent 60% of the respondent were Male and 40% were female as the objective was to study the impact of E-marketing on consumer purchase behaviour.

B. Age Group

Age Group	Response	
18-30 years	61	18-30 years
30-45 years	20	30-45 years
45-60 years	11	45-60 years
Less than 18 years	8	Less than 18 years
More than 60 years	1	Less than 18 years

Fig. 2: Age Group

Most of the respondents were from the age group of 18-30 years, followed by 20% of people from age category of 30-45 years, followed by 11% of people from age category of 45-60 years as well as 8% of the total respondents were from the age of less than 18 years and a very small portion of population comprising of 1% from 60+ age category.

C. Monthly Income

Fig. 3: Monthly Income

Income is one of the determinants of one’s socio-economic status in society. It is seen from Pie-chart that, 43% people belong to student category followed by 31% of respondents belong to high income category i.e. More than 50000 followed by 16% of the respondents belongs to middle level income category i.e., Rs 30000-50000 and rest 10% of the respondents belong to low-income category i.e., Below Rs 30000.

D. Do you prefer to E-Shopping?

Fig. 4: E-Shopping

The chart shows that most of the respondent think that buying online is beneficial and the remaining 3% of the respondent thinks that online shopping is not beneficial due the factors like forgery products, highly priced products and no guarantee of the product.

E. Does E-Marketing affect your Purchase Decision?

Does E-Marketing affect your purchase decision?	Response
Agree	25
Disagree	4
Neutral	41
Strongly Agree	31

Fig. 5: E-Marketing affect your Purchase Decision

40% of the respondents think that E-Marketing may or may be not affect Purchase decision of consumer while 31% of the respondents strongly agree about E-marketing affecting the consumer Purchase decision followed by 25% of the respondents agree to it while rest 4% of the respondents disagree regarding E-marketing affecting Consumer Purchase Decision.

F. Why do we prefer E-shopping?

Why do you prefer e-shopping?	Response
Availability of alternatives	21
Convenient	26
Cost effective	22
Time Saving	32

Fig. 6: Why do we prefer E-shopping

According to the survey, we found that Most of the respondents think that E-shopping is preferred by the people because it is Time-saving followed by 26% of the respondents think that E-shopping is convenient, 21% of the respondents think that E-shopping is cost effective because of the heavy discount given on most of the products and rest of the remaining respondents think that E-shopping is having the availability of products alternatives.

G. What types of E-marketing are you heard of?

E-marketing have you heard of	Response
Content Marketing	14
Email Marketing	4
SEO Marketing	16
Social Media Marketing	46
Web Advertisements	21

Fig. 7: types of E-marketing

According to the survey, we get to know that most of the people get aware about E- marketing through social media like Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp etc., while some of the respondents get to know through content marketing followed by 16% of the respondents get to know about E-marketing through Search Engine Optimization and rest of the remaining respondents get to know through E-mail Marketing.

H. What is your opinion on E-Marketing?

Opinion on e-marketing	Response
24X7 services	26
Buy the rare product	4
Convenient and Time Saving	23
Information Search	8
Low Price	15
Variety of products	25

Fig. 8: What is your opinion on E-Marketing

The chart reveals clearly the customer attitude towards e-marketing. Most of the respondents goes with both variety of products as well as 24*7 services followed by 23% of the respondents goes with convenience and time savings, 15% of the respondents goes with Low Price while some of the respondents goes with information search and buying the rare Product. Thus, the study infers that the convenience and time saving is an important factor to attract the customer towards e-marketing in the study area.

I. What is the Problem that Customer Faced while using E-Marketing?

Major problems that you come across while using e-marketing	Response
Confusion in selection of different brands of a product	12
Incomplete payment transaction	8
Lack of awareness of consumer	10
Lack of reliability in quality of product	441
Low speed of internet	7
Physical touch is not possible	237
	23

Fig. 9: Problem that Customer Faced while using E-Marketing

The analyse shows most of the respondents choose Lack of reliability in quality of product as the biggest problem while using E-marketing followed by Physical touch of product. Some of the respondents think that Confusion in selection of different brands of a product is also a big problem while using E-marketing followed by Lack of awareness of consumer, Incomplete payment transaction and Low speed of Internet.

J. Mode of Payment preferred while shopping via E-Marketing

Mode of payment do you prefer when shopped via e-marketing	Response
Cash on delivery	31
E-Payments	70

This question is continuation of the last one checking the security concerns of the Indians. It states that 31% of people still trust cash on delivery mode as compared to online paymentbut there are around 69% of people who trustsboth the modes. I think there is still a big trust issue among the Indian consumers regarding payment mode and if somehow this gap could be decreased it'd help in crossing a big-bar and would help in increase in the salesdrastically.

K. Major Products/Services Bought by Consumer via E-Marketing

Major products/services bought by you via e-marketing	Response
Apparels	44
Electronic Goods	17
Others	30
Ticket Bookings	10

Fig. 10: Major Products/Services Bought by Consumer via E-Marketing

The chart reveals that 43% of the respondents prefer Apparels as the most buying products followed by 30% of the respondents prefer others as their option, 17% of the respondents prefer electronic goods and 10% of the respondents prefer Ticket Booking.

L. Rating of Online Services: - E-booking

Rating of E-Booking online services	Response
1	1
2	2
3	4
4	
5	

SUMMARY OUTPUT

Regression Statistics

Multiple R	0.322063218
R Square	0.103724716
Adjusted R Square	0.195033712
Standard Error	15.563847
Observations	5

ANOVA

	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	84.1	84.1	0.347185909	0.597139931
Residual	3	726.7	242.2333333		
Total	4	810.8			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	11.5	16.32350044	0.704505755	0.531884002	-40.44866367	63.44866367	40.448664	63.4486637
X Variable 1	2.9	4.921720566	0.589224837	0.597139931	-12.76311143	18.56311143	12.763111	18.5631114

Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for E-booking online services followed by 3 out of 5. Only 9% of the respondents rated E-booking as Excellent online services while 7% of the respondents rated E-billing as poor online services.

- Here the dependent variable is People Response and independent variable is Rating of E-Booking online services. According to the analysis 32.20% strong relationship between these two variables.
- The second point is here 10.37% no. of people response is explained by the rating of E-booking online services as per the analysis.
- 19.50% is the average measure. That is the regression equation is over predict.

Here we get the P value 0.531884 & 0.59713. so that we will accept the null hypothesis. That means there is no significant relationship.

Fig. 11: Rating of Online Services: - E-booking

M. Rating of Online Services: - E-Billing

Rating of E-Billing online services	Response
1	3
2	16
3	33
4	36
5	13

SUMMARY OUTPUT

Regression Statistics

Multiple R	0.45325960
R Square	0.20544427
Adjusted R Square	0.059407
Standard Error	14.3619868
Observations	5

ANOVA

	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	160	160	0.775694893	0.443311235
Residual	3	618.8	206.2666667		
Total	4	778.8			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	8.2	15.0629789	0.544381032	0.624034764	-39.73712155	56.13712155	39.73712155	56.13712155
X Variable 1	4	4.541659021	0.880735428	0.443311235	-10.45358597	18.45358597	10.45358597	18.45358597

Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for E-billing online services followed by 3 out of 5. 13% of the respondents rated E-billing as Excellent online services while 3% of the respondents rated E-billing as poor online services.

Fig. 12: Rating of Online Services: - E-Billing

- Here the dependent variable is People Response and independent variable is Rating of E-Billing online services. According to the analysis 45.32% strong relationship between these two variables.
- The second point is here 20.54% no. of people response is explained by the rating of E-billing online services as per the analysis.
- 5.94% is the average measure. That is the regression equation is over predict.
- Here we get the P value 0.62403 & 0.44331. so that we will accept the null hypothesis. That means there is no significant relationship.

N. Rating of Online Services: Online shopping of Products and Services

Rating of online shopping of products and services	Response
2	6
3	22
4	43
5	30

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

	<i>Rating</i>	<i>How would you rate the following online services?</i>
Mean	3.5	25.25
Variance	1.666666667	239.5833333
Observations	4	4
Pooled Variance	120.625	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	-2.800629093	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.015569063	
t Critical one-tail	1.943180281	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.031138125	
t Critical two-tail	2.446911851	

Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for online shopping of Products and services. 30% of the respondents rated online shopping of Products and services as Excellent online services while only 6% of the respondents rated it as poor online services.

So, here I've done the t-test for better understanding. The value of P is less than 0.05 so, it rejects null hypothesis & accept alternate hypothesis.

Fig. 13: Rating of Online Services: Online shopping of Products and Services

O. Rating of Online Services: - E-Ticketing

Rating of E-Ticketing online services	Response
2	2
3	21
4	49
5	29

t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances

	Rating	How would you rate the following online services?
Mean	3.5	25.25
Variance	1.666666667	378.9166667
Observations	4	4
Pooled Variance	190.2916667	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	6	
t Stat	-2.229792109	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.033642579	
t Critical one-tail	1.943180281	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.067285158	
t Critical two-tail	2.446911851	

Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for E-Ticketing online services. 29% of the respondents rated E-Ticketing as Excellent online services while only 2% of the respondents rated E-Ticketing as poor online services.

So, here I've done the t-test for better understanding. The value of P is greater than 0.05 so, it is null hypothesis. There is no significant difference.

Fig. 14: Rating of Online Services: - E-Ticketing

P. Would you Recommend others to shop via E-Marketing?

Would you recommend others to shop via e-marketing?	Response
Maybe	17
No	1
Yes	83

Most of the respondents will recommend others to shop via E-Marketing because since the Covid 19 Pandemic, E-Marketing plays an important role in satisfying the needs for the products of consumers.

Fig. 15: Recommend others to shop via E-Marketing

X. FINDING OF THE STUDY

Purpose of study was had a thorough analysis regarding different attributes of e-marketing with age, gender & income of the respondents. Our analysis on the respondents showed various results.

- It was found that age group of 18-30 years filled the questionnaire. Main possible reason behind this may be that younger people are more technology oriented & also they maybe working in organizations where they need to work on computer and internet.
- Most of the respondents find e-shopping more convenient & time saving. A wide range of products/services with variety are available to choose from and also in general traditional shopping in India has never been pleasant for Indian consumers. There has been a mixed reaction in response to quality & authenticity of the products offered.
- Most of the respondents think cash on delivery is the right mode of payment because of the last one checking the

security concerns of the Indians. It states that 31% of people still trust cash on delivery mode as compared to online payment but there are around 69% of people who trusts both the modes. I think there is still a big trust issue among the Indian consumers regarding payment mode and if somehow this gap could be decreased it'd help in crossing a big-bar and would help in increase in the sales dramatically.

- The study finds out that the E-commerce platform has become a big giant and the Online mode of selling the products can be an effective and low-cost strategy for the sellers. Also, during and after the pandemic, this strategy would prove to be the one which would reap maximum benefit for the sellers with Social Media Marketing being the most preferable one almost 45% of the respondents think the same according to the survey report.
- 40% of the respondents think that E-Marketing may or may be not affect Purchase decision of consumer while

31% of the respondents strongly agree about E-marketing affecting the consumer Purchase decision followed by 25% of the respondents agree to it while rest 4% of the respondents disagree regarding E-marketing affecting Consumer Purchase Decision.

- The chart reveals clearly the customer attitude towards e-marketing. Most of the respondents goes with both variety of products as well as 24*7 services followed by 23% of the respondents goes with convenience and time savings, 15% of the respondents goes with Low Price while some of the respondents goes with information 20 search and buying the rare Product. Thus, the study infers that the convenience and time saving is an important factor to attract the customer towards e-marketing in the study area.
- The analyse shows most of the respondents choose Lack of reliability in quality of product as the biggest problem while using E-marketing followed by Physical touch of product. Some of the respondents think that Confusion in selection of different brands of a product is also a big problem while using E-marketing followed by Lack of awareness of consumer, Incomplete payment transaction and Low speed of Internet.
- The chart reveals that 43% of the respondents prefer Apparels as the most buying products followed by 30% of the respondents prefer others as their option, 17% of the respondents prefer electronic goods and 10% of the respondents prefer Ticket Booking.
- Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for E-booking online services followed by 3 out of 5. Only 9% of the respondents rated E-booking as Excellent online services while 7% of the respondents rated E-billing as poor online services.
- Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for E-billing online services followed by 3 out of 5. 13% of the respondents rated E-billing as Excellent online services while 3% of the respondents rated E-billing as poor online services.
- Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for online shopping of Products and services. 30% of the respondents rated online shopping of Products and services as Excellent online services while only 6% of the respondents rated it as poor online services
- Most of the respondents rated 4 out of 5 for E-Ticketing online services. 29% of the respondents rated E-Ticketing as Excellent online services while only 2% of the respondents rated E-Ticketing as poor online services.
- Most of the respondents will recommend others to shop via E-Marketing because since the Covid-19 Pandemic, E-Marketing plays an important role in satisfying the needs for the products of consumers.

XI. RECOMMENDATIONS

- The consumers get a lot of products at cheapest rate but they found lack of reliability in quality of the product. So, the online market must introduce number of products at cheapest rate without compromising in quality.
- The security features of a e-payment to be improved in future properly.
- E-marketers should take care about customer's feedback to improve their quality of services.

XII. CONCLUSIONS

E-marketing is transforming the way people do business all around the world at a rapid pace. E-marketing is a convenient way to shop. It has inspired a large number of personnel in both the private and public sectors. The most influential media is television commercials. Employees are affected by convenience, time savings, and pricing when it comes to e-shopping. The majority of responders are happy with the results of online marketing. The challenges with internet marketing are having a negative impact on the number of people who shop online.

Sales on the internet have increased dramatically in the business-to-consumer category during the last few years. Customers are becoming accustomed to the new shopping channel, which includes customers from both established and developing countries. Researchers and practitioners alike must understand the aspects that influence intention, adoption, and repurchase. E-marketing is growing popularity among people, particularly among the younger generation, but in today's environment, e-marketing will need to reach a greater distance to become equally popular among all age groups. People are hesitant to use e-services because of security issues, a lack of personal interaction with the product offered, delays in product delivery, and pricing and quality worries. Furthermore, people are less adaptable to emerging technology and are more resistant to change.

To determine the digital market's growth, numerous aspects must be considered, including online transaction security, personal privacy, convenience, price transparency, accessibility, time savings, and trust. The internet is one of the ways that customers' shopping and purchasing habits are changing. Because the majority of consumers use the internet to shop for products and compare pricing and features, businesses should be aware of how internet users feel about online shopping.

Foods, apparels, and electrical gadgets are the three industries where Indians spend the most, so all businesses in these areas should absolutely consider going online. One of the key challenges where organisations fail to grab potential customers' attention is advertising of webproducts and services. Companies should focus on providing educational advertisements that include product information as well as supplementary products and services that best meet people's needs. The frequency of such commercials should be high in order to position the items and brands in the thoughts of consumers. In a nutshell, we can conclude that e marketing has the potential to grow; nevertheless, adequate promotion, both at the producer and consumer levels, is required, in addition to government initiatives.

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